

RULE-BASED CONCEPT FOR DOSING DETERMINATION USING INTELLIGENT TOOLS

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to optimize dosing through the application of intelligent tools-methods. Here, the case study focuses on the flocculation phase of drinking water processing in a real system. Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS), regression, and "know-how" of the operators represented through linguistic expression as experiential knowledge are integrated to create a dosing calculation program. The goal is to establish a functional relationship between the process variables.

KEYWORDS: ANFIS; dosing; linguistic expression, regression, experiential knowledge

1 INTRODUCTION

When treating drinking water, it is important to meet two key requirements: to ensure that the water is safe for consumption and to minimize the costs of the treatment process. Overdose is increasing costs, while insufficient dosing disrupts water treatment process. By using the correct amount of coagulant-flocculent, two important goals are achieved. The first objective is to improve the efficiency of flocculation, which is an important step for water treatment. The second objective is to reduce the costs associated with the process. Typically, operators rely on their experience to determine the appropriate amount of dosing in processing facilities.

The JAR test simulates the coagulation-flocculation and sedimentation process in a water treatment plant and helps operators determine if they are using the right amount of treatment chemicals. However, in reality, the determination is delayed because it relies on the already changed properties of the raw water. Operators use their experience to verbally group certain values of the variables noted in the worksheets. In past in most cases, intelligent tools-methods were used for the purpose of optimization and modelling in water processing systems. This research integrates the use of these methods. In addition, these methods have application in other various fields. In researches (Soinangun & Asrol, 2022; Svalina et al., 2013; Valcic et al., 2011; Dimanoski et al., 2017; Yetkin & Ozfirat, 2016; Kahraman & Ulikan, 2003; Kahraman et al., 2004; Kahraman et al., 2015; Ozifrat, 2016) are shown the use of methods: ANN, Fuzzy Logic and Regression like valuable tools for optimization,

prediction and computing. In similar studies like our research, input data from surface water and operational data from dosage, are used to create models for the dosing prediction and control also using: ANN, Fuzzy Logic and Regression Analysis (Wan et al., 2010; Heddam et al., 2012; Trinh & Skang, 2010; Juntunen et al., 2012; Boruszenko et al., 2015; Naidoo & Van der Walt, 2013; Cooperative Research Centre (CRC) for Water Quality and Treatment, 2015). The primary goal of this study is to create a model (program) that could serve as a control unit. In this study, flow and turbidity of raw water and dosage of flocculent and coagulation solution are used as input-output variables. To establish the model, 240 pairs or 960 data were collected from the "Ilovica" treatment plant in Bosilovo, Republic of Macedonia, over of four years (Stojkov, 2019). This was done to provide a wide range of values for the variables and to cover different processing periods.

2 METODOLOGY

2.1 Water treatment process

The water treatment plant "Ilovica" has the ability to treat 3840 cubic meters of water per day or a maximum of 44 liters per second. The treatment process is fully automated and controlled by a Programmable Logic Controller, the stages (phases) are presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Different phase of Water Treatment

In order to effectively control the process, it is important to measure and record the variables being monitored. The way these variables are measured is determined by the existing monitoring system. Some variables are measured in real time using sensors embedded in the system, while others are measured manually using portable measuring devices.

Fig. 2 Built-In Sensors

2.2 Knowledge by operators

The goal of using experiential knowledge to find a solution is to relate the values of the input variables to the values of the output variables (Kasabov, 1996). The hidden knowledge, represented by historical data can be expressed as a vector (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ (n - number of pairs). Experienced operators can use their knowledge to determine processing rules and define the values of variables in groups, through linguistic expression. The number of selected if-then rules depends on the number of selected groups (subsets). This is shown in Fig. 3. Four distinct groups or subsets represent the qualitative definition of the range of values for the two input variables: small (C_1), medium-small (C_2), medium (C_3), big (C_4) for the flow of the raw water (x_1) and low (D_1), medium-low (D_2), medium (D_3), high (D_4) for the turbidity of the raw water (x_2). The optimal connection of input-output variables (flow and turbidity of raw water like input variables and amount of dosage of flocculent solution like output variable) in our case is set with "if-then" rules

(Figure 3). The calculations for each rule are done using Equation 1 separately, while for variables, Equation 2.

If x_1 is in A_i and x_2 is in B_j and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ ($n = 4$) then,

$$y = x_1 \cdot B_{1(i,j)} + x_2 \cdot B_{2(i,j)} + B_{0(i,j)} \tag{1}$$

$$z = y \cdot B_1 + B_0 \tag{2}$$

Where: A_i - groups (flow of raw water); B_j - groups (turbidity of raw water); x_1, x_2 - input variables (flow and turbidity of raw water); y - (input)output variable (amount of dosage of flocculent solution); B_0, B_1, B_2 - regression coefficients; n - number of groups (subsets), z - output variable (amount of dosage of coagulant solution)

Fig. 3 Selected „If-Then,, Rules

Before creating a non-uniform network partition, the number of variables and groups (subsets) to be used are determined. Then, learning methods are used to refine and optimize the previous parameters (Yen & Langari, 2019). This "fine-tuning" capability is used here, in order to determine the boundaries of each of the groups (subsets), as an intersection between two membership functions (Figure 3). The boundaries of each group (subset) used in the dosage calculation program are determined by general arithmetic calculation L^2 Norm Euclidean Distance (Equation 3) using the values of the membership function parameters. Obtaining the optimized values of membership function parameters was done by using an intelligent ANFIS (Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System) tool.

$$\|x\|_p = (\sum_{i=0}^n |x_i|^p)^{\frac{1}{p}} \tag{3}$$

2.3 Data preparation

If any of the variables listed in Table 1 change, it implies a change in the water treatment process in real time. In our case, water treatment is done by rapid treatment and pressure filtration, and as emphasized earlier, any change in the input variables directly affects the water treatment.

Table 1 Observed values of variables

	Flow	Turbidity	Dosage of flocculent	Dosage of coagulant
	m ³ /h	NTU	l/h	l/h
Maximum	161	99	130	89
Average	83	53	51	35
Minimum	29	6	16	11

The collected input-output pairs for a given criterion (a turbidity value of less than 0.100 NTU) it depends on the processing regime and the total volume in the treatment stage:

$$NS = VT / RP \quad (4)$$

Where: NS - number of samples in one observation; VT - total volume of phase treatment; RP - regime of processing.

Table 2 shows the water treatment stage, which consist of coagulation and flocculation, sedimentation and filtration volumes.

Table 2 Total volume of phase treatment

Steps of phase treatment	Volume (m ³)
Coagulation and flocculation	130.4
Sedimentation	120.4
Filtering	26.7
Total:	277.5

2.4 ANFIS (Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System)

ANFIS (Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System), introduced by Jang, is a rule-based approximation tool (Yen & Langari, 2019). A specific Sugeno type fuzzy system is presented, which is implemented in a five-layer feed-forward network structure (Jang, 1993). ANFIS uses "if-then" rules to determine output based on input values (Gorzalczany, 2002). ANFIS as an intelligent tool uses observed and historical data from operational lists to train. Such a tool can also be used in water treatment systems. (Wu & Lo, 2008). The ANFIS architecture we are using is a zero-order Sugeno fuzzy model. It includes two inputs, x1 and x2, and

one output, y. In Figure 4 is shown the general structure of ANFIS.

Fig. 4 Structure of ANFIS (Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System)

The hybrid Neuro Fuzzy tool ANFIS optimizes the parameters. These optimized parameters are referred to as "previous" parameters, while the constant values for the output are known as "consequential" parameters. ANFIS learning involves a combination of back propagation and Least Squares Estimation (Gorzalczany, 2002). Using the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox, the optimized parameters were obtained. To create a fuzzy approximation system, a network partition is imitated. The values of "previous" parameters that define the triangular fuzzy membership functions, obtained after optimization and which are used in the model shown in Figure 5, are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Triangular fuzzy membership functions

Linguistic expression	Values of parameters
Small	3.6; 4.78; 5.94
Medium-small	4.76; 5.94; 7.17
Medium	5.95; 7.09; 8.30
Big	7.13; 8.27; 9.45
Low	0.04; 4.92; 9.88
Medium-low	4.92; 9.89; 4.84
Medium	9.87; 14.84; 19.8
High	14.84; 19.8; 24.76

2.5 Linear regression

Linear regression is a method-tool used to identify the relationship between variables and the strength of that relationship. Dependence can be functional and statistical. The relation represents functional dependence:

$$u = f(v) \quad (5)$$

The relationship is shown by the equation:

$$u = f(v) + e \tag{6}$$

Where: $f(v)$ is a function component, and e - error component.

Here, we will use a linear regression models. These models are represented by the general formula:

$$u = q_0 + q_1 p_1 + q_2 p_2 + \dots + q_i p_i + e \tag{7}$$

The variable u is dependent in the given relationship, p_i are independent variables, $q_0, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_i$ are coefficients and e is stochastic variable (error). The functional dependence between the variable u and variables p_i is represented as:

$$u = q_0 + q_1 p_1 + q_2 p_2 + \dots + q_i p_i \tag{8}$$

A linear regression model shows how the variable u is related to the variables p_i , determined using samples (pairs). This model can be expressed as a system of n -relations.

Fig. 5 Path-procedure for obtaining the regression coefficients

In this research is used Regression tool in Excel to find the coefficients B_0, B_1 and B_2 used in Equation 1 and Equation 2. To determine the number of pairs for each rule used in dosing calculation program, an algorithm-program was developed in the C programming language. Obtaining the coefficients applied in the dosing calculation program (Figure 15) is show in the Figure 5.

3 RESULTS

The performance and indication of accuracy of the models is expressed through Mean Absolute Error (MAE) Equation 9 and with coefficient of

determination R^2 Equation 10, using 240 samples (pairs). The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Model performance

model	MAE	R^2
ANFIS-regression	0.063	0.980
regression	0.346	0.970

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|o_i - d_i|}{o_i} \tag{9}$$

Where: MAE - Mean Absolute Error; o - observed values; d - determined (predicted) values; n - number of samples.

$$R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - d_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n o_i^2} \right), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{10}$$

Where: R^2 - coefficient of determination; o - observed values; d - determined (predicted) values; n - number of samples.

The results of observed values of input and output variables shown in Figures 6, 7 and 8, and the determined (calculated) values of dosing of flocculent (0.15% solution of anionic flocculent) and coagulant (15% of solution of coagulant) shown in Figures 9 and 10. The calculation of dosing values of flocculent with Rule Viewer from MATLAB Fuzzy Logic Toolbox is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 6 Observed values of flow of row water

Fig. 7 Observed values of turbidity of row water

Fig. 8

Observed dosing values of flocculent

Fig. 9 Observed dosing values of coagulant

Fig. 10 ANFIS surface-determined flocculent

Fig. 11 Rule viewer-determination of flocculent

Fig. 12 Determination of coagulant

4 CONCEPT AND GRAPHIC PRESENTATION

Fig. 13 shows the concept of incorporating a dose calculation program into the dosing system as a control unit. Here the concept for dose determination, which graphically is presented trough diagram in Fig. 14.

Fig. 13 Controlling the dosing based on input variables

Fig. 14 Concept of dosing system

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IF x1 <= 5.35 AND x2 <= 7.40 THEN
  y := (x2 * 0.066) - (x1 * 0.009) + 5.301;
ELSIF x1 <= 5.35 AND x2 > 7.40 AND x2 <= 12.35 THEN
  y := (x1 * 0.649) + (x2 * 0.064) + 2.076;
ELSIF x1 <= 5.35 AND x2 > 12.35 AND x2 <= 17.32 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.455) + (x2 * 0.080) - 7.074;
ELSIF x1 <= 5.35 AND x2 > 17.32 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.591) + (x2 * 0.068) - 7.582;
ELSIF x1 > 5.35 AND x1 <= 6.53 AND x2 <= 7.40 THEN
  y := (x1 * 1.988) + (x2 * 0.280) - 6.300;
ELSIF x1 > 5.35 AND x1 <= 6.53 AND x2 > 7.40 AND x2 <= 12.35 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.335) + (x2 * 0.172) - 7.556;
ELSIF x1 > 5.35 AND x1 <= 6.53 AND x2 > 12.35 AND x2 <= 17.32 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.706) + (x2 * 0.142) - 9.428;
ELSIF x1 > 5.35 AND x1 <= 6.53 AND x2 > 17.32 THEN
  y := (x1 * 1.911) + (x2 * 0.111) - 3.832;
ELSIF x1 > 6.53 AND x1 <= 7.70 AND x2 <= 7.40 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.085) + (x2 * 0.153) - 6.157;
ELSIF x1 > 6.53 AND x1 <= 7.70 AND x2 > 7.40 AND x2 <= 12.35 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.667) + (x2 * 0.324) - 11.548;
ELSIF x1 > 6.53 AND x1 <= 7.70 AND x2 > 12.35 AND x2 <= 17.32 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.932) + (x2 * 0.297) - 13.172;
ELSIF x1 > 6.53 AND x1 <= 7.70 AND x2 > 17.32 THEN
  y := (x1 * 3.260) + (x2 * 0.004) - 10.366;
ELSIF x1 > 7.70 AND x2 <= 7.40 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.251) + (x2 * 0.356) - 9.079;
ELSIF x1 > 7.70 AND x2 > 7.40 AND x2 <= 12.35 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.147) + (x2 * 0.435) - 8.750;
ELSIF x1 > 7.70 AND x2 > 12.35 AND x2 <= 17.32 THEN
  y := (x1 * 2.217) + (x2 * 0.356) - 8.410
ELSE
  z := y * 0.69 - 0.112;
END_IF;

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Fig. 15 Rule –based dosing calculation program „if-then,, form

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The possibility of "flexible" control and application of the built-in equipment in a modern processing system has a crucial role in the fulfilment of the final task. This research aims to apply the world's scientific tendencies in the use of intelligent tools (methods) in the direction of advancement and improvement of the operation as a whole through optimization and modelling by applying the numerous data in the form of input-output variables. In this paper is presents a concept for determining

the dose of flocculent in a real water treatment system. Since there is no generally accepted mathematical correlation, i.e. the characteristics of coagulation-flocculation in water treatment systems are different; an important aspect in this research was the establishment of functional dependence between some of the "input" parameters (variables) with the chemical-physical process of coagulation-flocculation. In this paper, a dosing calculation program („ELSIF,,-statement), is developed in PLC platform,, Codesys,, in Structured Text (ST), with the possibility of applicability in a logic controller (Figure 15).The model was obtained by integrating hybrid Neuro Fuzzy tool ANFIS and Regression. The statistical indication, Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and coefficient of determination R^2 was used in order to determine the performance of the applied model.

The disadvantage of this model is the exponential increase of "processing rules" when increasing the number of input variables.

Advantages of this research, as well as future recommendations are:

A simplified,, if-then,, dosing program and cheaper computiunality for use in logic controllers.

Maintaining process robustness and possibility of implementation of other input-output parameters (variables) for water treatment such as: conductivity, acidity (pH), temperature, color, UV absorption, i.e. doses of solutions for coagulation-flocculation and disinfection.

Measurements performed in real time by all embedded processes meters-transmitters, and from which operational data is collected (recorded), can be applied in order to obtain conceptual models such as dosing systems.

The implementation of other process measurements in real time, such as conductivity measurement in order to manage coagulant dosing, as well as research on the replacement of coagulants using "electrocoagulation" which is a coagulation process without the use of chemicals for coagulation.

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